

About the useful uselessness and unimportant importance of mathematics

Gustavo Bruno, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, ✉ gustavo.bruno@estudiante.uam.es

Natalia Ruiz-López, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid

In this presentation we explore the symbolic power of mathematics and mathematics education (ME), focusing on the trait of the socio-political perception of usefulness-importance of mathematics. We contribute excerpts from discussion groups with students from 2nd and 3rd year of secondary education, from a public school of Madrid. Then, we analyse and discuss those excerpts with the aim of understanding how the students live through school mathematics and its aforementioned “usefulness-importance”.

Introduction

This chapter is an excerpt (and adaptation to the theme of this MES conference) of a chapter from a recently finished doctoral thesis (Bruno, 2020). Which in turns is heavily influenced by the young tradition of the socio-political perspectives in mathematics education (ME), as explained by Valero & Pais (2015), along many other authors. As we explain and elaborate throughout the mentioned Thesis, from a socio-political perspective in ME, the phenomena of the mathematics class or of the school cease (to a greater or lesser extent, as Valero & Pais, 2015, explain) to be the exclusive center of research attention. And they are understood as a fundamental, but not exclusive, node of an interweaving of social practices of different kinds: technologies of power and government, devices for evaluation and accreditation / social stratification, global agendas, dominant cultural discourses and evaluations, creation of subjectivities through schooling, “regimes of truth” (in Foucauldian language), and so on. All of them indeed closely related to mathematics, their schooling, and research in ME.

A relevant issue, both in the doctoral research and in the theoretical approach there adopted, is what authors like Skovsmose (1994) and Sáenz and García (2015) call the *symbolic power* of mathematics. We characterize this *symbolic power* (based on the developments of such authors) with the following fundamental features:

- Mathematics is considered an objective knowledge, aseptic of any ideological-political interest or struggles, neutral in values.
- Mathematics have, politically / symbolically, an almost unappealable truth value (“ideology of certainty”, according to Skovsmose & Borba, 1997). “The numbers speak for themselves / they don’t lie.”
- Mathematics is very useful / important (“for everything”, “they are everywhere”, “in science and technology...but hey, also in the arts and... and in everyday life”). And

Please cite as: Bruno, G., & Ruiz-López, N. (2021). About the useful uselessness and unimportant importance of mathematics. In D. Kolloosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 1, pp. 341–348). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5393662>

therefore they are/should be a significant component of any educational curriculum in any country/community that claims to be up to date on any timeline of progress and innovation.

- Furthermore, considering the global aspirations of democratization, equity, social justice, “global citizenship” promoted from high levels of international organizations (i.e., the UN 2030 agenda; UN, 2015), teaching-schooling in Mathematics is promoted as a universal right / duty, as a key element to achieve such aspirations. Valero (2017) genealogically analyzes this ideal of “Mathematics for all” and how it has been developing in recent decades.

However, despite this broad socio-cultural legitimation, for a large part of the “ordinary people”, mathematics is impenetrable or incomprehensible, if one does not have an important level of initiation and practice with them (i.e., university degree or profession that applies them in depth). Therefore, Mathematics has the remarkable political-cultural position of being a symbolic system that is both accepted and legitimized, but largely misunderstood and even feared-rejected by a large part of the population (Spanish, world). In our experience, both as mathematics teachers at different educational levels and as researchers in ME, this fear-rejection could be related to the systemic and generalized phenomenon of school failure in mathematics.

Now, considering the enormous embedding that mathematics has in decision-making and power spaces (in states, in international agencies, in economic and financial schemes, in electoral systems, in health systems, in modern ICT, even in the understanding/measurement of space-time...) the political consequences of this status of symbolic power of Mathematics are far-reaching. As expressed by Sáenz and García (2015, p. 26):

By presenting itself so legitimized and at the same time so impenetrable for the uninitiated, it goes so far as to make the dominated assume the legitimacy of their submission [...]. Clouded in the shadow of this unattainable knowledge, anyone who ignores the language and mathematical methods by which social processes are usually expressed remains unarmed, without an answer, sometimes he must accept his bad luck, quietly waiting until the wisdom of who decided for him bears fruit.

As a part of a doctoral thesis project, field work has been developed in different Secondary Education schools in Madrid, Spain. The students involved are from 2nd and 3rd year of secondary education (“ESO”, by its acronym in Spanish).

In the field experiences mentioned above, we seek to investigate the different aspects of the “symbolic power” of mathematics. In this presentation we will communicate some results referring to the socio-political and cultural *importance-usefulness* trait assigned to mathematics and its education.

For that purpose, we studied the perceptions and experiences of the participating students about mathematics and school math, considering different points of view: difficulty, liking or rejection, being a “person of sciences” or being a “person of letters”, self-concept, etc. A significant part of the inquiries was around the question of the importance-usefulness of mathematics (in society, in daily life, in school, etc.).

Methodology of research

In her doctoral thesis, Suavita (2017) proposes an operational construction around the notion of *social imaginary*, that is, both notions and theoretical framework, as a methodology to study these socio-political, cultural and historical phenomena. His thesis is entitled “Imaginaries in mathematics teachers in training”. Among others, Suavita collects the developments of the Ibero-American Research Network on Imaginaries and Representations (RIIR), which in turn bases its theoretical frameworks on the research of Castoriadis, Durand, Maffesoli, Baeza, Carretero, Silva and others.

In this chapter we follow her methodological approach in her study of social imaginaries. One of the main techniques she uses for obtaining data and evidence is the *focus group* or *discussion group*, and we thus will apply it for addressing our research concerns.

We organized the participant students in up to 7 focus groups, and in those we proposed to the students the discussion around topics that implied the trait of the use-importance of mathematics, like: why is mathematics taught in school? What are they used for in different areas of life? Why are they (or are they not) important-useful?

Mathematics are useful-useless, but not really important-unimportant

We will now transcribe excerpts from some of the discussion groups relevant to *use-importance* trait, and its perception by the participant students. We will follow each with analysis and commentaries considering the theoretical perspectives posited above.

The “R” abbreviation means “Researcher”, the person who was conducting the discussion groups. The other abbreviations refer to the names of the participant students.

Group 1:

- R: Let’s see, one more question: if you’re not good at math, can you be a sciences person?
(The students discuss, argue a bit before answering)
- R: And if you are good at math, can you be a letters person?
- A3: I’m bad at math, and I’m going for sciences.
- A1 (to A3): And are you going for sciences? Well, not me, because I believe that everything is united, you know [...] That if you don’t know mathematics, then, as you progress, you will not know physics and chemistry either, which is what is happening to me.
- L (to A3): For example, Physics and Chemistry are not mathematics[sic], but there are formulas... and they are mathematics after all.
- R: And if you were bad at math, it wouldn’t be convenient for you to do science, or would it be convenient...?
- A3: Let’s see, for the career I want to do, yes. Because that also depends on what you want to do. I, for example, want to be a midwife.
- A1: And what use is mathematics for you to get a child? One-two-three!
- A2: Three minus one, two, minus one, one...
- A3: If I want to go for that profession, then I must go for sciences. Then it [mathematics] will be useful to me. Let’s see, math is useless to me, but it is necessary in sciences, so it’s a no brainer.

We first observe that A3 classmates themselves question the decision to “follow a sciences degree”, because science has/is a lot of math; or, without math there is no science, or without math you cannot do sciences. And they affirm it empirically, because at least in the current schooling-accreditation system, this is considered true. Whether or not math is used in one or another discipline, study, trade or criminal activity, to do “science” and anything that has been so labeled, you have to go through many and difficult math... and their assessments.

Of course, the issue of the usefulness of mathematics for an obstetrician is a sweet plate of non-sense, but we will return to it later.

Group 2:

- C: Math is a bummer, but it is very important.
- Q: That depends on what you study ...
- R: And if you did not study engineering or “sciences”, would they be useful to you? (Controversy, mixed voices).
- B1: In certain things, yes. But like, above all, if you have a subject that has to do with mathematics. For example, if you go to “Sciences” ... also in “Letters” I think you must do mathematics. Or maybe it helps me to know the area of a certain something if I study Plastic Arts. But there are a lot of things that have nothing to do with what we are going to do.
- S: But, for example, if I want to study psychology, mathematics will not help me to study psychology. For example, “basic math”, as we said before, in real life does work for me, but ...
- B1: In everything we have lived through, we haven’t used a square root at all. Rule of three I have used, very few, but square root for nothing, knowing the apothem of whatever, either... I do not walk down the street calculating apothems.
- R: And, for example, if any of you were a journalist ... Do you think math could help you to be a good journalist?
- B: All knowledge helps you to come to more knowledge. But I think it could also do well without math. That you can do better, yes. But if you do not like it, why are you going to put in the effort? [sic!]
- R: Do you think I could use math in a particular situation as a journalist?
- E: For example, maybe you have to do a survey, and for that you do need math.
- B2: You must calculate the schedule, what time do you have to be to do certain something...
- B1: But, for example, with the survey, you can hire a worker to do it. But, to calculate the time, you need “basic” math, you don’t need to know a rule ...
- S: But, the basic thing, what we use in life, is addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division, and studying the hours. And the percentages, that is it.
- L: Yes, things that are of no use to you. For example, equations of the second degree, me, not at all. I mean, and I am terrible at these.
- E: Sure, imagine that you are a lifeguard, you are not going to calculate the distance you must jump to catch [someone drowning] ... it is already dead in the water.

About the useful uselessness and unimportant importance of mathematics

The first answer of the students is an automatic “it’s very important (despite its ugliness)”, i.e., a conformity with the socio-political trait we mentioned at the beginning of this presentation. But shortly afterwards, the contradictions, questionings and even ironies emerge again, as in the first group. It seems that math is not so valuable in everyday life, but also in many professional activities; is useful mostly for those things labelled as “science”, whatever that means. Only basic and elementary school math has proven to be useful to them.

Group 3:

- R: Why do you think math is compulsorily taught in ESO?
G: It is something we have to know... at least a minimum.
A: For our future, I don’t know, so that we can...
S: There is always the same excuse. What are you studying it for? To approve the test, but...
G: Let’s see, until the ESO, it’s fine. Then, more math, well ... whoever wants to aspire, well.
[...]
R: How do you see it?
S: Well, I say, math is going to be used and such, but to a certain extent. There are other things that you look at or whatever, but because you have to approve it. But that’s the excuse you’ve always been given. You study it, whatever, because you have to pass. Because another thing’s, what are you going to use them for?
G: I don’t know, it’s what they made us do. Study to pass, and the same with everything.
[...]
J: Man, people have to perfect themselves, and humanity also, if we stayed at a certain point, we could never move forward, we could not help other people.
G: But it’s considered good [sic] to study just to pass. And not that they teach you to learn. Because, if you study it, you will forget it; If you learn it, it will stay with you. Someday you will forget, but ...

It is again difficult for students to justify the supposed importance-usefulness of school mathematics, at least from what they are studying in the ESO courses (2nd-3rd year at the time of the discussion groups). In general, the immediate or automatic response is “because we have to know it-it’s very important-it’s good for life”. But then the doubts and questions appear...

¡No, wait! Math is important, you have to study it “to pass” (the test, the courses), to “be approved” ... to go on with more studies. To progress.

And beyond that, it’s not so clear for the students.

Group 4:

- R: What do you think mathematics is taught you for, and what do you think mathematics is used for? Please be sincere.
D: Let’s see, mathematics is taught, really speaking, to teach us (sic!) ... to know how to unwind...
(J. laughs at the non-sense)
D: J. you’re going to take one...

- J: (ironic)... Mathematics is taught and used to teach...
- D: Yes, they are taught because if you don't know mathematics, you will hardly know anything else...
- J (sarcastic) But also, they are used to teach ...
- D (annoyed) He won't let me finish the sentence... do you want to shut up? I didn't say that...
(Brief argument)
- D: Anyway, we said... mathematics seems to me to be necessary, as J. said. It is "necessary" that they teach it. But sometimes I also thought that it is a lot to give #@*%*...
- M: And that there are times when they are not understood ... Why do I have to learn this formula, or five hundred thousand formulas [...], if then maybe a mathematics teacher comes to give classes or is going to dedicate to some math, and he is going to go to the notebook and look at the formulas ... Why do you have to learn those formulas? Sometimes it doesn't make sense.
- D: Because if they don't understand it then they won't know how to explain it ...
- R: I mean, but you, think about it, why are Mathematics taught to you ...
(Discussion)
- D: Let's see, let's be clear. Mathematics give a lot of #@*%*. And even more so when we are... consider that mathematics can make you repeat a whole course where you are doing well, and because you don't pass math, you repeat the course! I mean, that's really annoying!
- R: If you don't pass math and language, you repeat the course. That is fashionable, it has become fashionable.
- All: Yes, yes.

"They are important-useful because they teach us and they are useful-important." In all the discussion groups of the research experiences emerged some variant of what is shown in these excerpts: in a first automatic response, someone affirmed that mathematics "is very important-useful"; but shortly after the discussion began, the supposed importance-usefulness of math was either (not) justified with non-sensical expressions, or it was quickly questioned by the group. That is, there are contents of the school mathematics that are too abstract (difficult, without context?). And it is not at all obvious how they would be used in "daily life" (or in most careers, professions, vices, felonies); they may be used in specialized applications of certain professions, in "sciences" or for "engineers", not in "everyday life". Arguments of "common sense", but arguments after all...

All in all, in the discussion groups emerged a marked skepticism about the importance-usefulness of school mathematics, despite the first norm-conforming automatic responses.

However, another *sense-event* comes to light, perhaps more clearly in the last excerpt: the compulsory nature of school math, and its strong character of selection/exclusion through the assessment device. There are many expressions like "you study them because you have to pass", and D.'s elegant rhetoric in the last excerpt. Math is useful, but not really, and yet, they are tough and compulsory and can jeopardize the future perspective of students. What?

Let's go back now to the student who wanted to study obstetrics: school mathematics would hardly be important-useful in her intended profession, at the time of assisting in childbirth (we can't imagine how an obstetrician would need to calculate the sum of an infinite series at that given moment; perhaps we are wrong ...). But if she doesn't perform "well" on school math (that is, high enough grades), she won't be able to earn enough political credits to be a midwife. It is not difficult to extend this idea to the paradox of useless-usefulness of school mathematics: "you have to study them to approve them, because they will be useful to you, not in themselves (rather the opposite, they are applied little to nothing in most circumstances of "daily life" and many trades); but because if you do not pass them or do not have good enough grades, your personal possibilities in the future will be limited". Assessment, the sine-qua-non device of this stratification machinery, is implicit in all these disquisitions and *non-sense*...

Non-sense in a plate: math is useful and useless, essential but not really important...

Prudentia

In his own personal experience as students (teen and adults), we never had major problems with math and even enjoyed studying them... However, about tastes and colors... mathematics is a very particular discipline, and even when taught wonderfully, the students may or may not like it ... no, yes?

Well... we are also a bit fed up with seeing over and over the same disconnected, non-sensical, useless topics with our students; repetitive assessments, the suffering in our own flesh of the failures of our students and having to repeat again and again ... What we did not personally experienced in person of this selection/exclusion system, we are living it now through our present students. (And yet, somehow, we need the failure of the students... because in part we gain our bread out of it, and this chapter is and the participation in this conference is partially financed with that income...).

Furthermore, the students do not have such a naïve perspective, nor do they lack a critical view of the arbitrariness of ME, as a selection/exclusion mechanism; and of the doubtful importance of the "contents" of school mathematics, in daily life. We do not necessarily agree with the perceptions and evaluations of the students (rather, the opposite in many cases...). It cannot be denied that in their own way, the kids question some features of the symbolic power of mathematics and ME, as explained in the first part of this chapter.

So yes... there is something paradoxical, non-sensical, in the students' perception regarding the importance-utility of mathematics. Somehow, like in a Lewis Carroll novel or an El Chavo del Ocho episode, they consider mathematics useful and useless, important and unimportant, at the same time. What can the students, their teachers, we researchers, do about it?

Well, first of all acknowledge that, most likely, we also have a lot of paradoxes and internal, repressed non-senses about the sociopolitical place of mathematics, ME and the school as political technologies. So, we adults can, at least in principle, assume that this intrinsic tension is present.

As Cancino (2011) explains, in the individual psyche-social imaginary tension, "society imposes socialization on the psychē through its institutions." In contrast, "the psychē imposes an essential requirement on the social institution: the social institution must provide it with meaning" (Cancino, 2011, p. 73; Castoriadis, 2002, p. 268).

So, we also propose to interpret this non-sense as a way of experiencing the symbolic power of mathematics. More precisely, as a way of conforming their (our) own subjectivity in face of the symbolic power of mathematics, and especially of ME and school mathematics as technologies of selection/exclusion and/or accreditation/stratification in contemporary capitalist societies.

Valero and Pais, in an article from 2015, summarize:

What if school mathematics is not important in society due to the exceptional and intrinsic characteristics of the academic field that gives this school subject its name, but rather due to the place it occupies within a particular social configuration of power? [...] A political approach thus assumes that the teaching and learning of mathematics are not neutral practices, but that they insert people –be it children, youth, teachers, adults– in socially valued mathematical rationalities and forms of knowing. Such insertion is part of larger processes of selection of people that schooling operates in society. It results in differential positioning of inclusion or exclusion of learners in relation to access to socially privileged resources such as further education, labor market, cultural goods, etc. (Valero & Pais, 2015, p. 178).

As Gilles Deleuze elaborates in *La logique du Sens* (1969), *non-sense* and paradox are intrinsic to *sense*. Either in the proposition or in the (emerging) event and singularity, *non-sense* allows for the operation of *donation of sense*. By exploring (exploiting without mercy) these internal tensions of *non-sense* we attempt to reveal some chin in the armor of the symbolic power of mathematics (education).

References

- Borba, M., & Skovsmose, O. (1997). The ideology of certainty in mathematics education. *For the Learning of Mathematics*, 17, 17–23.
- Bruno, G. (2020). *Educación matemática y justicia social: Una experiencia de aprendizaje y servicio solidario* [Doctoral dissertation, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid].
- Cancino, L. (2011). Aportes de la noción de imaginario social para el estudio de los movimientos sociales. *Polis, Revista de la Universidad Bolivariana*, 10(28), 69–83.
- Castoriadis, C. (2002). *Figuras de lo pensable*. Fondo de Cultura Económica.
- Deleuze, G. (1969). *Logique du sens*. Les éditions de Minuits.
- Sáenz, C. & García, X. (2015). *Matemáticas: Placer, poder, a veces dolor. Una mirada crítica sobre la matemática y su enseñanza*. UAM ediciones.
- Skovsmose, O. (1994). *Towards a philosophy of critical mathematics education*. Kluwer.
- Suavita, M. (2017). *Imaginarios del profesorado en formación sobre las matemáticas: Hacia una cultura matemática para la justicia social* [Doctoral dissertation, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid].
- UN General Assembly (2015). Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. <https://www.refworld.org/docid/57b6e3e44.html>
- Valero, P. (2017). Mathematics for all, economic growth, and the making of the citizen-worker. In T. S. Popkewitz, J. Diaz, & C. Kirchgasser (Eds.), *A political sociology of educational knowledge: Studies of exclusions and difference* (pp. 117–132). Routledge.
- Valero, P., & Pais, A. (2015). Examining political perspectives in mathematics education. In C. Bergsten & B. Sriraman (Eds.), *Refractions of mathematics education* (pp. 173–196). Information Age.